

Data collection Peak detection MS2Dec Identification Adduct Alignment Mobility Isotope tracking

Mass accuracy

MS1 tolerance: Da

MS2 tolerance: Da

⬆️ Advanced

Data collection parameters

Retention time begin: min

Retention time end: min

Mass range begin: Da

Mass range end: Da

Isotope recognition

Maximum charged number:

Consider Cl and Br elements:

Multithreading

Number of threads:

Execute retention time corrections

Load

Together with Alignment

Finish

Cancel

Deconvolution parameters

Sigma window value:

MS/MS abundance cut off: amplitude

⬆️ Advanced

Exclude after precursor ion:

Keep the isotopic ions until: Da

Keep the isotopic ions w/o MS2Dec:

MSP file and MS/MS identification setting

MSP file: LipidMsmsBinaryDB-VS66-FiehnO.lbm2

Select

Retention time tolerance: 100 min

Accurate mass tolerance (MS1): 0.01 Da

Accurate mass tolerance (MS2): 0.05 Da

Identification score cut off: 80 %

Use retention time for scoring: Use retention time for filtering:

⬆ Advanced

Text file and post identification (retention time and accurate mass based) setting

Text file:

Select

Retention time tolerance: 0.1 min

Accurate mass tolerance: 0.01 Da

Identification score cut off: 85 %

Spectrum cut off and report option

Relative abundance cut off: 0 %

Only report the top hit:

Load

 Together with Alignment

Finish

Cancel

Adduct ion setting

User-defined adduct

Molecular species	Charge	Accurate mass [Da]	Included
[M+H] ⁺	1	1.00782503207	☒
[M+NH ₄] ⁺	1	18.03437413	☒
[M+Na] ⁺	1	22.9897692809	☒
[M+CH ₃ OH+H] ⁺	1	33.03403978207	☐
[M+K] ⁺	1	38.96370668	☐
[M+Li] ⁺	1	7.01600455	☐
[M+ACN+H] ⁺	1	42.03437413207	☐
[M+H-H ₂ O] ⁺	1	-17.00273964793	☒
[M+H-2H ₂ O] ⁺	1	-35.01330432793	☒
[M+2Na-H] ⁺	1	44.97171352973	☒
[M+IsoProp+H] ⁺	1	61.06533991207	☐
[M+ACN+Na] ⁺	1	64.0163183809	☐
[M+2K-H] ⁺	1	76.91958832793	☐
[M+DMSO+H] ⁺	1	79.02176103207	☐
[M+2ACN+H] ⁺	1	83.06092323207	☐
[M+IsoProp+Na+H] ⁺	1	84.05510919297	☐
[2M+H] ⁺	1	1.00782503207	☒
[2M+NH ₄] ⁺	1	18.03437413	☒
[2M+Na] ⁺	1	22.9897692809	☒
[2M+3H ₂ O+2H] ⁺	1	56.04734410414	☐
[2M+K] ⁺	1	38.96370668	☐
[2M+ACN+H] ⁺	1	42.03437413207	☐
[2M+ACN+Na] ⁺	1	64.0163183809	☐
[M+2H] ²⁺	2	2.01565006414	☐
[M+H+NH ₄] ²⁺	2	19.04219916207	☐

Load

 Together with Alignment

Finish

Cancel

Alignment parameters setting

Result name:

Reference file:

Retention time tolerance: min

MS1 tolerance: Da

⬆️ Advanced

Retention time factor: (0-1)

MS1 factor: (0-1)

Peak count filter: %

N% detected in at least one group: %

Remove features based on blank information:

fold change

Keep 'identified' metabolite features:

Keep 'annotated (wo MS2)' metabolite features:

Keep removable features and assign the tag:

Gap filling by compulsion:

Method Mass spectrum Formula finder Structure finder Data source Retention time

Search option

- Spectral database search
- Formula prediction and structure elucidation by in silico fragmenter

Spectral database option

- Use internal experimental library (MassBank, GNPS, ReSpect)
- Use in silico spectra for lipids (LipidBlast) Solvent type: HCOONH4
- User-defined DB

Precursor ion option

- Precursor oriented spectral search

Information

In the case that you have EI-MS (GCMS) spectra for spectral database search,

1. uncheck 'Precursor oriented spectral search'
2. check 'TMS-MEOX derivative compound' at 'Formula finder' tab.
3. set the same mass tolerance for both MS1 and MS2.

*The above thing is not the case for structure elucidations by accurate EI-MS spectra.

Finish

Cancel

Method Mass spectrum Formula finder Structure finder Data source Retention time

Mass tolerance setting

Mass tolerance type: Da ppm

Mass tolerance (MS1): +-Da or ppm

Mass tolerance (MS2): +-Da or ppm

Abundance setting

Relative abundance cut off: %

Mass range setting

Mass range max: Da

Mass range min: Da

Finish

Cancel

Method Mass spectrum Formula finder Structure finder Data source Retention time

Formula calculation setting

LEWIS and SENIOR check:

Isotopic ratio tolerance: %

Element ratio check: covering

Element probability check:

Element selection

O N P S F Cl Br I Si

TMS-MEOX derivative compound

Minimum TMS count:

Minimum MEOX count:

Options

Maximum report number: up to 100

Time out (-1 means infinite): min

Advanced settings for AIF:

Setting

Finish

Cancel

Method Mass spectrum Formula finder Structure finder Data source Retention time

In silico MS/MS or EI-MS fragmenter setting

Tree depth: [1-3]

Use the fragmentation library for electron ionization (EI)

Use the fragmentation library for low energy CID

Options

Maximum report number: up to 100

Time out (-1 means infinite): min

Finish

Cancel

Local Databases

- HMDB (Human) Urine (Human) Saliva (Human) Feces (Human)
- Serum (Human) CSF (Human) SMPDB (Human) LipidMAPS (Lipids)
- YMDB (Yeast) ECMDB (E.coli) BMDB (Bovine)
- FooDB (Food) PlantCyc (Plant) ChEBI (Biomolecules)
- T3DB (Toxin) DrugBank (Drug) STOFF (Environment)
- KNApSAcK (Natural product) NANPDB (Natural product)
- PubChem (Biomolecules) UNPD (Natural product)

User-defined DB

MINEs (Metabolic In silico Network Expansions) setting

- Never use it. Only use when there is no query in local DBs. Always use it.

PubChem Online setting

- Never use it. Only use when there is no query in local DBs. Always use it.